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Evaluating emotional and subjective responses in synthetic art-related dialogues: A multi-stage framework with large language models

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ABSTRACT

The appearance of Large Language Models (LLM) has implied a qualitative step forward in the performance of conversational agents, and even in the generation of creative texts. However, previous applications of these models in generating dialogues neglected the impact of 'hallucinations' in the context of generating synthetic dialogues, thus omitting this central aspect in their evaluations. For this reason, we propose an open-source and flexible framework called GenEvalGPT framework: a comprehensive multi-stage evaluation strategy utilizing diverse metrics. The objective is two-fold: first, the goal is to assess the extent to which synthetic dialogues between a chatbot and a human align with the specified commands, determining the successful creation of these dialogues based on the provided specifications; and second, to evaluate various aspects of emotional and subjective responses. Assuming that dialogues to be evaluated were synthetically produced from specific profiles, the first evaluation stage utilizes LLMs to reconstruct the original templates employed in dialogue creation. The success of this reconstruction is then assessed in a second stage using lexical and semantic objective metrics. On the other hand, crafting a chatbot's behaviors demands careful consideration to encompass a diverse range of interactions it is meant to engage in. Synthetic dialogues play a pivotal role in this context, as they can be deliberately synthesized to emulate various behaviors. This is precisely the objective of the third stage: evaluating whether the generated dialogues adhere to the required aspects concerning emotional and subjective responses. To validate the capabilities of the proposed framework, we applied it to recognize whether the chatbot exhibited one of two distinct behaviors in the synthetically generated dialogues: being emotional and providing subjective responses, or remaining neutral. This evaluation will encompass traditional metrics and automatic metrics generated by the LLM. In our use case of art-related dialogues, our findings reveal that the capacity to recover templates or profiles is more effective for information or profile items that are objective and factual, in contrast to those related to mental states or subjective facts. For the emotional and subjective behavior assessment, rule-based metrics achieved a 79% of accuracy in detecting emotions or subjectivity (anthropic), and an 82% on the LLM automatic metrics. The combination of these metrics and stages could help to decide which of the generated dialogues should be maintained depending on the applied policy, which could vary from preserving between 57% to 93% of the initial dialogues.

1. Introduction

Recently, the release of pre-trained LLMs to the public (Brown et al., 2020; Touvron et al., 2023) has put NLP in the focus of society and science, evidencing some of the limitations of these models such as their hallucinations (Buchanan & Shapoval, 2023), tail phenomena (how to respond in unlikely situations) (Kandpal, Deng, Roberts, Wallace, &

Raffel, 2022) and sometimes undesirable behaviors related to ethical issues towards minorities (Bender, Gebru, McMillan-Major, & Shmitchell, 2021)(e.g. gender (Basta, Costa-jussà, & Casas, 2019), race (Tan & Celis, 2019), etc.) due to the bias that normally exists in the training data. As a consequence of this concern, several regulatory bodies are creating rules of conduct to increase transparency in the data and models, as well as raising awareness about the risks that they entail (Kop, 2021).

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Despite these undesirable characteristics, undoubtedly these LLMs have brought advances in several fields, especially in those areas in which capturing data is a delicate and restrictive task due to the sensitive condition of the participants, such as in health-related studies or education (Javaid, Haleem, Singh, Khan, & Khan, 2023; Qiu, He, Zhang, Li, & Lan, 2023). Not only these models can be presented as an option to generate synthetic data (Qiu et al., 2023), but also for exploring new approaches and giving a more personalized education, encouraging autonomy, and competence, significantly enhancing student support, and building a more effective learning environment (Alqahtani et al., 2023; Javaid et al., 2023).

Nonetheless, there exist many questions about the successful performance of the models in different domains, especially in those cases in which there is no public, scientific and detailed information about the employed datasets to train the models, such as ChatGPT, Claude, or BARD. For this reason, it is required to apply them to obtain benchmarks to evaluate their capacities in multiple domains, in an attempt to understand their limitations and capabilities. Discovering the lack of these LLM will shed light on the next steps the research community should follow to solve them by creating new datasets or fine-tuning LLMs with domain-specific information (Ji et al., 2022), among other possibilities. Additionally, there are still open questions about how to measure certain ‘personalities’ or ‘flavors’ of the chatbots and which algorithms are optimal for achieving these specific behaviors. The effective generation of dialogues eliciting these desired behaviors is crucial for the chatbot’s training. It enables the chatbot to recognize specific situations and learn how to handle them appropriately. For instance, a chatbot can be programmed to express emotions, opinions, preferences, and feelings, imbuing its responses with a human touch. Similarly, the chatbot can exhibit emotional behaviors by conveying a spectrum of feelings like ‘sadness,’ ‘fear,’ ‘excitement,’ and more. Alternatively, it might be designed to remain neutral and devoid of personal sentiments.

Unlike research in the area advances fast, we are still at the initial stage of disentangling what is behind the black boxes these models represent. Moreover, it also fails to address the issue of incorporating certain personal characteristics into conversational agents. Hence, the contributions of this paper could be summarized in:

- As the data generated from LLMs are representations of the internal structure and knowledge of the LLM employed, the first proposal is a framework to generate guided dialogues between a human and a ‘personalized’ chatbot following a recipe structure. The analysis of them would indicate the performance of the specific models and their limitations, which also contribute to explaining their behavior.
- We developed a two-path automatic evaluation methodology employing LLM assessment and external traditional metrics based on rules to address the evaluation of the generated characteristic and contextual information by the LLM against the data requested in the prompt.
- Finally, to contribute to a faster and further understanding of LLMs in other domains, we released the platform with the proposed framework for allowing replication of our methodology in other domains and with different chatbot characteristics.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents related works on the generation of dialogues from LLM and existent evaluation approaches. Section 3 summarizes the proposed methodology, including the generation and evaluation pipelines proposed. Section 4 describes the art domain use-case in which the framework was evaluated, the datasets employed, and the specific set-up for performing the experiments. Section 5 presents the results and discussion. Finally, in Section 6 we summarize the main conclusions of our study and propose future research lines.

2. Related works

In this section, the related works will be introduced. First, we will classify the existing generative models and frameworks related to our proposal. Next, we will explain and present the most employed evaluation methodologies in the literature to assess the performance of LLMs.

2.1. Generative models and frameworks

Generative and Large Language Models (LLM) can be classified into 2 possible families which vary in their architectures, way of processing inputs, and abilities to solve different tasks:

- Causal Language Models (CLM): This family of models is composed of those models that receive a sequence of past tokens and their mission is to predict the next token based on past information. This characteristic of relying on past information implies that they are unidirectional. Some examples of these types of models are GPT-3 (Brown et al., 2020) or Llama-family (Touvron et al., 2023), among others. These models have demonstrated remarkable performance in tasks implying generating large chains of text.
- Masked Language Models (MLM): This second family of models receives at its input a sequence of tokens, but unlike CLM, some of the tokens are unknown (or masked) and the task is to predict which token is the most probable to fit in that position. Furthermore, the architectures are also different since they can attend to past and future information. This bidirectionality gives them the capacity to exploit a larger context, being better in classification tasks (sentiment or emotion prediction (Qin et al., 2023; Talaat, 2023), depression detection, (Ji et al., 2022), topic modeling (Abuzayed & Al-Khalifa, 2021), etc.). BERT is probably the most representative model of this group (Devlin, Chang, Lee, & Toutanova, 2019).

Although it is possible to have this separation, most are based on the transformer architecture, considering only the encoder module or the encoder and decoder.

As it was commented, all models can be used to generate text, but the ones achieving the highest performance are the CLM. Among them, ChatGPT (GPT-3 (Brown et al., 2020)) has the highest impact on the general public. Nevertheless, it still could present a lack of knowledge towards certain domains or ethical aspects (as stated in Bender et al. (2021)); which encouraged the exploration of its capacities. Moreover, it is one of the state-of-the-art Generative AI solutions that has been employed previously in other domains in generative tasks (Qiu et al., 2023); hence, any distillation of knowledge from new domains could reveal limitations and future lines of investigation. Among other research interests, it was pre-trained on millions of dialogues, which normally implies the assumption that it contains information from a large representative sector of societies, nationalities, and contexts; impossible to acquire in a reasonable period of time.

Attempting to exploit this characteristic for creating synthetic data, some frameworks have been proposed for extracting dialogues. For instance, in Qiu et al. (2023) the methodology employed to generate multi-turn dialogues in Chinese consisted of extracting single-turn interventions between a user suffering from a mental health disorder and a clinician from the PsyQA dataset (Sun, Lin, Zheng, Liu, & Huang, 2021), which then are fed into ChatGPT to create the extended version of the dialogues to training a mental health support chatbot. Similarly, Wang et al. (2023) proposed the Self-Instruct framework to generate tasks automatically of different natures starting initially from a pool of tasks that are augmented with new tasks generated by the LLM, (which was the procedure followed for creating the Alpaca dataset). Additionally, the LLM is also in charge of deciding and annotating the response given

for a specific task e.g. if the task is to generate an argument against or in favor of abortion, the LLM generates the text and specifies whether it can be considered in favor or against the issue. Another dataset in line for employing self-instruction is Vicuna (Chiang et al., 2023), collected from ‘Share-GPT.com’ web which contains posts created by users with their tasks and the responses given by ChatGPT. In this manner, it is possible to create automatically annotated and generated datasets.

2.2. Dialogues evaluation methodologies

As a result of the automatically generated frameworks, there is also an increasing interest in annotating synthetic data to understand its embedded knowledge and whether there exist biases that could be transferred to the models trained with them. In this regard, previous studies have proposed traditional metrics, based on formulas (or rules) and more recently LLM evaluations provided by pre-trained Large Language Models.

2.2.1. Traditional metrics

In the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP), several metrics have been proposed for evaluating different tasks, from Machine Translation to summarization.

In this regard, traditional metrics can involve those based on rules and formulas, such as some of the most commonly employed in machine translation (Chauhan & Daniel, 2022): BLEU (Papineni, Roukos, Ward, & Zhu, 2002), NIST (Doddington, 2002), ROUGE (Lin, 2004) and METEOR (Banerjee & Lavie, 2005), among others. Apart from these, others also highlight due to their simplicity, providing information about lexical matches as the Word Error Rate (WER) (Su, Wu, & Chang, 1992) or the Jaccard Index (Jaccard, 1912). All these metrics are appropriate for being employed in any task that requires a recovery of an original sentence or a syntactical comparison between two texts.

Likewise, when the task is more specific, e.g. in emotion or opinion recognition, other more concrete tailored metrics should be incorporated to explain these concepts. Among these metrics, dictionary-based metrics, such as VADER (Hutto & Gilbert, 2014) or the metric implemented in TextBlob for measuring subjectivity in sentences (Loria, 2018), could report valuable information about the appearance of these emotional or sentimental concepts in the text.

Due to the evolution of technology, metrics extracted from pre-trained systems are starting to be considered as part of this group. This is the case for example of the embeddings extracted from SBERT that are employed in several tasks for assessing semantic similarities between words or sentences (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019a). Other BERT-derived models have been fine-tuned to perform classification on emotion recognition (Talaat, 2023) or toxicity detection (Dale et al., 2021), which opens the opportunity of generating annotations of different dimensions that can provide a better understanding of the content of textual data without requiring human annotations, which is a time and economic-consuming resource. Other examples of metrics of this type could be BERTScore (Zhang, Kishore, Wu, Weinberger, & Artzi, 2020) or BLEURT (Sellam, Das, & Parikh, 2020). Nevertheless, this research area is constantly growing and new metrics and neural models appear in the literature to evaluate automatically different criteria in texts and dialogues.

2.2.2. Large language models-based metrics

Unlike formula-based, deterministic metrics and BERT-based models, with the apparition of LLMs, some recent works are starting to inspect the evaluation capacities of these large models in different domains. In that regard, the Self-Instruct framework includes an annotation stage accomplished by the LLM (Wang et al., 2023). Similarly, in Yang, Ji, Zhang, Xie, Kuang, and Ananiadou (2023) ChatGPT model is evaluated following a zero-shot strategy on several datasets for performing emotion and depression recognition. Moreover, in Yang, Zhang, Kuang, Xie, and Ananiadou (2023), ChatGPT is employed for

evaluating mental-health disorders and reasoning about the answers given by the model on a zero-shot style, and in a posterior stage, training a Llama model with the collected data from the zero-shot analysis for learning on that tasks (Lin & Chen, 2023; Liu, Iter, Xu, Wang, Xu, & Zhu, 2023).

Although several attempts have been made to increase the explainability of these models, it is still unclear how to know that they are committing ‘hallucinations’; hence, the main drawback of employing exclusively LLM self-assessment metrics is that responses of these models could be uncertain for domains in which they have ‘lacks of knowledge’ or for those cases that are unlikely (tail phenomena). Still, they could be considered a good option for being combined with classical objective metrics in order to provide more robust evaluations.

2.2.3. Human annotations

To conclude, depending on the task (e.g. generative AI, text classification, etc.) and the domain (general, health, education, etc.) metrics could vary since some could be more sensitive or the concept to model is more subjective (emotion, empathy, motivation, etc.). For instance, content generation requires higher human intervention in the annotation process since the outputs of these models are consumed directly by people and have to be aligned with their expectations. In this line, methods such as Chatbot-Arena (Zheng et al., 2023) or ‘ACUTE-EVAL’ (Smith et al., 2022) have been proposed. The first is based on a crowd-sourced battle platform in which users maintain conversations with two chatbots simultaneously and rate their responses based on their preferences, and the second, ‘ACUTE-EVAL’, is a methodology in which the user is asked to select among two texts which one matches better with a given feature or definition. Finally, other approaches include a phase for collecting human annotations to train the models with this feedback, as in the Reinforcement Learning with Human-in-the-Loop methods employed in models like Llama-2 (Touvron et al., 2023), to improve utility and safety in their chatbot answers; or PARTNER-model (Sharma, Lin, Miner, Atkins, & Althoff, 2021), focusing on annotating data for creating more empathetic chatbots trained over the learned weights of the DialoGPT model (Zhang, Sun, et al., 2020).

Despite the numerous benefits of these types of metrics, as it is also stated in Smith et al. (2022) or Mehri et al. (2022), these approaches also have their limitations, as the amount of agreement (decreasing when the subjectivity of the task increases), and the statistical sensitivity. Moreover, other issues that appear are the lack of standardized methods, or the absence of metadata from the annotators, which is critical in subjective tasks (e.g. when you consider labeling trustworthiness, maybe your culture, previous experiences, or age may influence your judgments). Finally, the main drawback of these manual methods is that they require high economic and temporal costs, not available in many cases, especially when expert knowledge is required (e.g. mental health (Garg et al., 2022)). However, recent studies show that LLM models have demonstrated similar human performance in annotating data in open domains (Lin & Chen, 2023).

3. Materials and methods

This section describes the generation, evaluation, and verification methods employed to assess the quality of the synthetically generated dialogues. Fig. 1 shows the modules of the framework, including a first-generation stage in which dialogues are obtained, and several evaluation stages employing traditional metrics (rule-based or formula-based) and LLM-assessment metrics generated by the LLM, as well as a profile recovery stage.

Regarding the evaluation of the characteristics, in this paper, we refer by characteristic to a specific behavior that the chatbot can display during the conversation; specifically, we explore and propose the concept of anthropic, which will be explained in the remaining sections.

Fig. 1. Overview of the GenEvalGPT framework for generating synthetic dialogues and evaluating their characteristics employing tailored and LLM-Assessment metrics. A final verification stage is also considered to study consistency between generation and evaluation.

3.1. Generation framework

As introduced before, this article proposed to employ a large generative model to extract dialogues. However, rather than generating random dialogues, we focused on creating tailored dialogues with embedded characteristics that could be evaluated in posterior stages to control the ‘hallucinations’ introduced by the LLM. These dialogues could be maintained between a user and a chatbot or between two users, in which one takes the role of an expert in a specific domain. Both will be profiled according to certain fields, as well as a domain (e.g. art, films, music, health, etc.).

Therefore, the first stage consisted of a prompt engineering process to design the prompt to incorporate structured data, similar to dictionaries which we called ‘Profiles’.

Each profile contains key–value fields, in which the key represents the name of a specific requirement and the value represents the expected behavior associated with that requirement that should be reflected in the dialogue. Table 1 displays a generic prompt that could be completed with customized profiles since the framework is flexible and modular to allow it. In Section 4, we will illustrate this idea applied to the art domain.

Table 1

Sample of a general prompt that may accept different profiles and fields providing contextual information about the expected dialogue for being generated by ChatGPT.

System	“You are an expert who talks about <TOPIC>”.
Prompt	Create a dialogue between an expert and a User with a minimum of N turns in the context of <CONTEXT> considering the following information below. <DOMAIN>Profile: - Field A: Metadata of field A related to the domain to study. - Field B: Metadata of field A related to the domain to study. <CHATBOT>Profile: - Field C: Metadata related to the chatbot.

This template accepts different types of fields and profiles which could be categorized as objective or subjective depending on the nature of their content. According to this category, for example, fields related to emotions, goals, or preferences would be integrated into the subjective category, whereas fields related to factual information (e.g. painting title, artist name or artistic movement) would be included in the objective category.

As the proposal was intended to be employed in research studies for analyzing and acquiring datasets with dialogues, the second stage after generating the prompt template is to address the automatic completion of each field. Three strategies were considered for automatizing the acquisition process, reducing the workload of filling in the profiles manually:

- Auto-completion from Structured Data: In this first case, the value of each key field is extracted from a structured type of data, which could be for example a column of a CSV, or a field of a database.
- Auto-completion from random lists: In this second case, the values are selected randomly from an externally provided list.
- Manual: In the last case, those fields completed manually in the template are maintained constant for all the dialogues generated.

After completing the templates of the profiles, the final step is to call the LLM API to create the dialogues.

3.2. Evaluation framework

To evaluate and validate the quality of the generated dialogues and their correlation with the original profile, we followed a three-step verification process, combining automatic metrics generated by the LLM and traditional metrics (e.g. WER, BLEU, VADER, etc.). As commented in Section 2.2, each metric could have its advantages and drawbacks; hence, their combination could provide robustness to the evaluation process to verify that the stated fields in the profiles were correctly integrated into the generated dialogues.

3.2.1. Lexical and semantic recovery evaluation

In this first stage, the aim is to recover the original template of the profile from the generated dialogue in an automatic fashion. The hypothesis is that if the dialogue contains all the values of the specified fields in the template, they should be identified in this recovery process again by the LLM. More details on the prompt template employed appear in [Appendix B](#).

Once the LLM generates the response, by auto-completing the fields of each profile, the next step is comparing the original profile with the generated profile. For this second step, classical rule-based metrics were selected to evaluate their similarities from two perspectives focusing on a literal lexical recovery (presence of the same words), or a semantic recovery (same meaning). Although more metrics could be implemented and included in the platform in the future, currently the analysis was performed with the Jaccard Index ([Jaccard, 1912](#)), Accuracy, Levenshtein Distance, WER ([Su et al., 1992](#)), BLEU-1 ([Papineni et al., 2002](#)), and a cosine similarity metric calculated between the embeddings of the reference sentence and the recovered sentence (more details about metrics can be consulted in [Appendix D](#)).

3.2.2. Characteristic evaluation

Unlike profile recovery metrics for evaluating semantic and lexical similarity, which can be employed in any scenario for filling in automatically empty fields, the characteristic evaluation (e.g. expert characteristic) requires a more elaborated process:

- First, a prior **definition of the characteristic** has to be decided, for our use case, we coined the term ‘Anthropic’ as the characteristic of ‘expressing emotions OR giving personal opinions, preferences, or subjective judgments’, as we will see in [Section 4.2](#).
- Second, it is necessary to identify **tailored (or traditional) metrics** based on rules or on pre-trained models, that can verify that the characteristic is present in the dialogues.
- Finally, the third stage for evaluating characteristics is the **LLM-Self-Assessment metrics**. This choice was motivated by the high capacity demonstrated by LLMs in modeling human language, as well as their capacity to perform automatic evaluations employing prompt-engineering techniques, as was demonstrated in previous publications ([Finch, Paek, & Choi, 2023](#)). From a technical perspective, to generate these automatic metrics, first, the definition of the characteristic has to be separated into single statements that the model can classify as ‘True’ or ‘False’ to judge the different aspects that belong to the specific characteristic. Subsequently, the response of the LLM to these statements is combined with boolean algebra operations (AND, OR) to recover the original definition and assess whether dialogues accomplish it.

3.3. Verification framework

After accomplishing the profile recovery and characteristic evaluation, the final stage would be to pass dialogues through a verification step to decide which dialogues should be maintained, or discarded depending on the expected quality-number of dialogues balance.

In this sense, two policies are proposed:

- **Conservative policy:** This policy aims to select high-quality dialogues. Therefore, we establish the requirement of maintaining only those dialogues in which all the metrics match and agree to the considered ground truth of the profile.
- **At least 1-coincidence policy:** This second policy is less strict in the quality criteria, focusing on maintaining more samples. The proposal for this policy is to keep all the dialogues in which at least one of the metrics matches the ground truth of the profile. Hence, only those dialogues in which there is no agreement

between the profile and any of the metrics are discarded since they are considered not following the expected criteria of the original profile.

At this point, it is important to remark that the generated dialogues could be employed for different tasks; hence, some dialogues could be discarded for a task (e.g. emotion recognition) but not for others (e.g. training conversational agents). Different tasks could be defined using each of the fields that appear in the profile, and the described methodology should be applied to have a common dataset with the capacity for being exploited on multiple tasks.

4. Experimental set-up for the use case of art domain

The GenEvalGPT framework was evaluated in an art-related domain, employing the Artemis dataset ([Achlioptas, Ovsjanikov, Haydarov, Elhoseiny, & Guibas, 2021](#)). Artemis contains 454,684 utterances explaining the viewer’s feelings to 80,031 unique artworks from 1119 artists and 27 art styles. During the annotation stage, participants additionally had to indicate what emotion the artwork transmitted to them from the following eight: anger, disgust, fear, sadness, amusement, awe, contentment, and excitement; plus an additional option called ‘something else’ if the artwork did not match any of the 8 previously mentioned emotions. However, as art perception and emotions are eminently subjective, the triggered emotion of the annotators for the same artworks may vary, although in [Achlioptas et al. \(2021\)](#) they state that in 45.6% of the cases, the majority selected the same emotion. Regarding the differences in emotions per valence, positive emotions (amusement, awe, contentment, and excitement) represent 62% of the answers, whereas negative emotions (anger, disgust, fear, and sadness) agglomerates the 26.3%, being ‘something else’ the chosen option in the 11.7% of the cases. For our scenario, the main usefulness of using this dataset falls on its metadata which was employed to contextualize our specific domain by extracting: (1) the painting title, (2) the author, (3) the triggered emotions with the highest consensus, and (4) the artistic movement of the artwork, which are the fields employed in one of our profiles defined as the ‘Painting Profile’.

4.1. Art-related dialogues generation

For the generation stage, we selected 24 artworks for the development set from the Artemis dataset collection balanced in terms of its majority voted emotion from the 100 most popular artists in the dataset (understanding by popularity those painters with a higher number of artworks in the Artemis dataset). Moreover, those with a higher agreement in triggered emotions were preferentially selected. Variations of the dialogues of this set came from:

- The metadata of the artwork used to complete the painting profile.
- The Expert characteristic of the expert profile, in which 2 values were studied: anthropic or neutral.
- The emotion of the user in the User profile, in which three possible values could be assigned: neutral, the first most voted emotion evoked by the artwork in the Artemis dataset, or the second most voted triggered emotion (whenever it existed). Additionally, we filtered the emotion ‘something else’.

This set of 100 dialogues was intended to perform the selection of parameters of the GenEvalGPT framework, as well as to study the possibility of employing LLMs to generate synthetic data of quality with reliable annotations. In our experiments, we worked with an instance of gpt-3.5-turbo-0301 accessed through the Azure API.

In addition, another set with 730 dialogues was generated and used as the test set to evaluate the optimum parameters discovered on the development set and study the expected performance in new dialogues. This set was created from the 176 artworks selected considering the

500 most popular artists, following the same criteria and variations explained before for the development set.

The extracted metadata was employed to complete the structure of the template of the prompt. To illustrate this idea, Table 2 contains a sample of a completed prompt. As it can be observed, we employ these three profiles:

- **The Painting profile:** This profile includes relevant information for the domain to study; in our selected use case: art. For this reason, the sample has information about the painting to discuss in the dialogue, which contains four fields: the painting title, the artists who painted the artwork, the most commonly triggered emotion in viewers, and the artistic movement the painting belongs to. This information will be extracted from the Artemis Dataset.
- **The Expert profile:** This second profile defines the expected behavior and goal of the conversational agent. In the depicted sample, this profile contains two relevant characteristics: The ‘Expert characteristic’ which refers to the capacity of the conversational agent, and the ‘Expert goal’ which refers to the role of the chatbot, its expected behavior or patterns to follow.
- **The User profile:** This profile considers the information of the user, which might include internal emotional and mental states, personality, preferences, etc. In the use-case example, five fields were proposed for profiling the users: their emotions at the moment, their roles (e.g. teacher–student), their preferred artistic movement, and two open characteristics to give further details about the user.

Table 2

Sample of a prompt providing contextual information about the expected dialogue for being generated by ChatGPT. There are three profiles: a Painting Profile, an Expert (or chatbot) profile, and a User profile.

System	“You are an expert who talks about a particular painting”.
Prompt	<p>Create a dialogue between an expert and a User with a minimum of 10 turns in the context of a museum considering the following information below.</p> <p>Painting Profile:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Painting title: By the eure river 1911 - Artist name: Gustave Loiseau - Typical triggered emotion in viewers: Contentment - Artistic movement or school: Post impressionism <p>Expert profile:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expert characteristic: The expert is neutral and does not provide personal emotions, opinions, preferences, feelings and tastes. - Expert goal: The expert is an intelligent tutor who teaches the user about different aspects of a particular painting. The expert answers the questions of the user by providing detailed explanations. Then, the expert also asks several questions to the user to test his or her knowledge and understanding capabilities about the painting information. <p>User profile:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User emotion: Neutral - User role: The user acts as a student that sometimes provides correct answers while others not to the questions. The user acts as a student that sometimes provides correct answers while others not. The user asks personal questions to the expert asking for feelings, emotions, opinions. - User preferred artistic movement: Contemporary realism.

4.2. Three-stages evaluation

For the first evaluation stage, we employed the same lexical and semantic metrics commented in Section 3.2.1 to evaluate the accurateness of the recovered profiles.

For the second stage of ‘Characteristic Evaluation’ of the framework (See Section 3.2.2), we defined the expert characteristic of ‘Anthropic’ as the characteristic of ‘expressing emotions’ OR ‘giving personal opinions, preferences, or subjective judgments’. Regarding the

tailored metrics, for the ‘Anthropic’ use-case we selected solutions considered as baselines for sentiment analysis and opinions mining in previous works (Achlioptas et al., 2021; Silva et al., 2022; Zhu et al., 2023):

- **Valence Aware Dictionary for sEntiment Reasoning (VADER) (Hutto & Gilbert, 2014):** This system is a rule-based sentiment analyzer that rates text according to valence and arousal comparing inputs with a selected gold-standard sentiment lexicon and employs grammatical and syntactical pre-defined rules derived from common human expressions used to transmit positive or negative sentiments, as well as intensity. This system returns a score between -1 (negative valence) and 1 (positive valence), representing the valence axis described in the psychological study of the circumplex model of affect Posner, Russell, and Peterson (2005). For this reason and its standardized use in research, it was selected to assess the emotional load of the generated dialogues and the responses of the LLM.
- **Subjectivity score:** For assessing the subjectivity vs. objectivity of the textual responses of each turn, a rule-based algorithm from the TextBlob library (Loria, 2018) was employed. The subjectivity metric measures the amount of personal opinion in a sentence varying between 0 (more objective) and 1 (more subjective). This metric was selected to measure how subjective were the answers given by the chatbot.

Finally, to obtain the LLM assessments on the ‘Anthropic’ characteristic, the aspects to evaluate are the emotional load of the responses and their subjectivity. After a prompt engineering process, the selected statements for achieving Yes/No responses were:

- The Expert expresses emotions.
- The Expert is giving personal opinions, preferences or, subjective judgments.

For our use case, the two statements presented before are passed to an OR operator to obtain the Anthropic or non-anthropic judgment to classify the agent’s attitude in the dialogue.

4.3. Verification framework

In this scenario, both policies were evaluated (conservatory and at least 1-coincidence) to compare their balance in the number and quality of the selected dialogues according to the Anthropic characteristic in the dialogues.

5. Results and discussion

In this section, we present the experiments performed for generating and evaluating the ‘anthropic’ characteristic of the expert in the dialogues by studying the results of the metrics and comparing different policies for discarding dialogues.

5.1. Results of the generation

The 100 generated dialogues of the development set contained on average 20.19 turns (min = 13, max = 35, STD = 5.36); for the test set the average number of turns of the 730 dialogues was 23.14 (min = 9, max = 39, STD = 5.64), with balanced interventions of the user and the expert.

Although in the prompt, instructions about the number of turns were given, with the sentence: ‘with a minimum of X turns’ of the prompt displayed in Table 2, the LLM was not always able to incorporate this information into dialogues. Some possible hypotheses could be: (1) the LLM does not distinguish what a turn means (i.e. one person-chatbot interaction, or a chatbot or person single-interaction), (2) the number of turns is not independent of the profile requirements

(e.g. if we require that the chatbot acts as an instructor asking and answering questions and we try to force the number of turns to 10, this number could be too short for creating a realistic dialogue), (3) the prompt could accept improvements. In future lines, we will perform experiments to deep into this problem.

5.2. Results of the evaluation framework: Profile recovery

As it was introduced in Section 4.1, the prompt for generating the dialogues contained 3 profiles: Painting Profile, Expert Profile, and User Profile. As part of the evaluation stage, described briefly in Section 4.2, these profiles were recovered automatically by sending the dialogue to GPT 3.5 with the empty template to allow the LLM to complete it. In this sub-section, we will explain the results obtained from the recovery phase by applying a lexical and semantic analysis only for the Jaccard Similarity and the semantic similarity metrics since conclusions are similar for the rest of the metrics. However, the reader can find more information on the Word Error Rate, Accuracy, Levenshtein similarity, and BLEU-1 in the Appendix D.

Starting with the ‘Painting Profile’, we can observe in Fig. 2 that the Jaccard index is close to 1.0 for objective fields, such as the painting title, the artist name and the artistic movement that the artwork belongs to; on the contrary, subjective fields as it is the typically triggered emotion of the artwork in viewers is more complex to be recovered, which is a reasonable result considering the complexity and variation of emotions that can appear in a conversation when discussing the evoked feelings when observing an artwork. Similar results can be observed for the semantic similarity plot of Fig. 3. For all the fields the major concentration of the distributions occurs around 1.0 (the maximum similarity) except for some outliers that appear for the fields of ‘triggered emotion’ and ‘artistic movement’.

Fig. 2. Jaccard Similarity plots calculated on the development set for each field of the Painting Profile. The highest, the best.

Fig. 3. Semantic Similarity plots on the development set calculated for each field of the Painting Profile: Painting title, artist name, typically triggered emotion in viewers and artistic movement or school. The highest, the best.

From a research perspective, these results indicate that more clues should be given to the LLM to improve its recovery capacity. For example, it could be possible to provide a list of options to select the

most appropriate given the context. Withal, the average Jaccard index for this field is 0.79, which indicates that few errors are committed compared to the reference value introduced in the profile.

Regarding the Expert Profile, the Jaccard index (See Fig. 4) indicates that there exist several words in both fields (‘Expert characteristic’ and ‘Expert goal’) that differ between the original profile and the recovered by the LLM from the dialogue. The most probable reason for these low values is that the definitions of what is a ‘characteristic’ or what is a ‘goal’ are not evident from the template (i.e. only from the keyword of ‘Expert characteristic’ there may exist other possible options to auto-complete that field employing the dialogue). Additionally, the values introduced in these fields were verbose to indicate to the model how the dialogues had to be generated. Consequently, when the model has to recover the verbose definitions, it makes mistakes trying to replicate the same words. A future solution to explore would be to indicate in the recovering template a list of possible values, as it was commented for the triggered emotions field; or analyze partially the sentence, focusing for example exclusively on the adjectives and adverbs.

Fig. 4. Lexical similarity metrics calculated on the development set for each field of the Expert Profile: Expert characteristic and expert goal. The highest, the best.

Moving to the semantic metric in Fig. 5, values are relatively higher compared with the lexical (or word-based) metrics, which suggests that although words’ coincidence is not perfect, the recovered fields are similar in meaning to those provided in the profile.

Fig. 5. Semantic similarity metrics calculated on the development set for each field of the Expert Profile: Expert characteristic and expert goal. The highest, the best.

For the user profile, we observe some of the previously discovered phenomena. When the fields are subjective (e.g. ‘User emotion’) the Jaccard index is lower compared to the semantic scores, the same can be observed when the name of the passed field is not too specific (e.g. ‘User characteristic 1’) since the LLM responses with a detected user characteristic which could not be the expected field or behavior in the original profile.

However, in this profile, the ‘User preferred artistic movement’ field drags the attention since the data-points position reveals two different behaviors (see the two Gaussian distributions of Figs. 6 and 7).

After analyzing the 100 dialogues according to their Jaccard index for this specific field, we discovered that in 42 of the cases rated with $J = 0.0$, the answer of the LLM was ‘Not specified’ for 38 of them, ‘None specified’ for one, it did not provide an answer for 2, and only 1 was a real mistake (‘Symbolism’ was recovered instead of ‘Cubism’).

Fig. 6. Jaccard Similarity plots calculated on the development set for each field of the User Profile. The highest, the best.

For the 3 cases with a $0 > J \geq 0.5$, the answer included the sentence ‘mentioned in the dialogue’; hence, as the artistic movement contains few words (AVG: 1.67, STD: 0.70), the Jaccard index calculated decays under 0.5. For the other 55 cases, the style was recovered correctly ($J = 1.0$).

Finally, Fig. 7 displays semantic similarities between the recovered and the original profiles of the User. It is possible to observe that for ‘User emotion’, the obtained average is higher than in the Jaccard index but still low, which may indicate that some of the recovered emotions could be semantically speaking closer in the valence-arousal space but still not being recovered as with the same name. In conclusion, probably these metrics will improve passing a list of emotions instead of letting the model guess without giving extra clues.

Fig. 7. Semantic Similarity plots calculated on the development set for each field of the User Profile: User emotion, User role, and User preferred artistic movement. The highest, the best.

This analysis indicates that dialogues might not include all the fields specified in the prompt or that the LLM might have failed on the recovery step, which reinforces the necessity of employing more metrics and stages to evaluate each field, as the ones that will be presented in the next sub-section for the anthropic characteristic.

5.3. Results of the evaluation framework: Anthropic characteristic of the expert

As was demonstrated before, relying uniquely on the output of the LLM to complete (or recover) the initial template could not be enough to understand whether complex concepts have been incorporated correctly into the dialogue. In this section, we will evaluate the ‘Expert Characteristics’ introduced in the template under the Expert profile. This characteristic can take two different values:

- ‘The expert is neutral and does not provide personal emotions, opinions, preferences, feelings, and tastes’. We will refer to this scenario as the Non-Anthropic.
- ‘The expert expresses emotions, opinions, preferences, feelings, and tastes’. We will refer to this scenario as the Anthropic.

Dialogues are balanced in these two dimensions, 50 should be ‘Anthropic’ and 50 ‘Non-Anthropic’ for the development set according to the specified values in the original template. In what follows, we will present the results from the traditional and the LLM-Assessment metrics.

5.3.1. Results of the tailored rule-based metrics

Fig. 8 displays the results of applying tailored rule-based metrics (valence and subjectivity) for each dialogue of the development and test sets, respectively. Each point represents the average value given to the expert of the dialogue, calculated as the average of all the interventions of the chatbot (or expert) in that dialogue.

Fig. 8. Metrics for evaluating the ‘Anthropic’ characteristics of the experts in the development set. The X-axis is the valence of VADER, and the Y-axis is the subjectivity score of TextBlob. Pink circles indicate dialogues whose ground truth is ‘Anthropic’, and blue crosses, ‘Non-Anthropic’.

Results reveal that one of the metrics is more informative than the other, specifically, subjectivity scores seem more robust when linear thresholds are established to divide the dialogues, as displayed in Table 3.

Table 3

Bi-variable linear threshold scan for sentiment (the absolute value of valence) and subjectivity over the development set of 100 dialogues. Optimum value is highlighted in bold ($th_{subjectivity} = 0.6; th_{valence} = 0.0$).

	Accuracy (%)	Valence threshold										
		-	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9
Subjectivity threshold	0	50	56	63	68	62	57	60	60	51	50	50
	0.1	50	56	63	68	62	57	60	60	51	50	50
	0.2	50	56	63	68	62	57	60	60	51	50	50
	0.3	50	56	63	68	62	57	60	60	51	50	50
	0.4	50	56	63	68	62	57	60	60	51	50	50
	0.5	62	65	68	72	67	60	62	61	51	50	50
	0.6	79	78	76	77	73	66	64	61	51	50	50
	0.7	57	57	57	57	55	54	53	53	51	50	50
	0.8	52	52	52	52	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
	0.9	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
1.0	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	

To measure accuracy, a rule-based operation was implemented, predicting as non-anthropic those dialogues with values under the fixed thresholds for at least one of the metrics (absolute valence or subjectivity); the rest are considered ‘anthropic’. Next, the accuracy is

Table 4

Bi-variable linear threshold evaluation on the test set for sentiment (the absolute value of valence), and subjectivity metrics over the test set of 730 dialogues. Optimum value is highlighted in bold ($th_{subjectivity} = 0.6; th_{|valence|} = 0.0$).

Accuracy (%)	Valence threshold											
	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0	
Subjectivity threshold	0.5	60.9	62.0	63.0	62.6	62.5	61.9	62.5	57.8	51.4	50.0	50.0
	0.6	68.4	67.5	67.1	66.0	63.6	61.8	60.3	55.2	50.7	50.0	50.0
	0.7	53.0	53.0	52.9	52.7	52.5	51.4	51.4	50.7	50.0	50.0	50.0

calculated by comparing these decisions with the ground truth (what was specified in the initial profile). Unlike other approaches based on machine learning, this approach was adopted as a baseline to understand what to expect from the rule-based metrics compared to those generated by the LLM, which will be presented in the next subsection.

To conclude the rule-based metrics analysis, we repeated the same procedure on the 730 dialogues that conform to the test set. Table 4 indicates that the optimum selected thresholds for the validation set (Table 3) are consistent when a larger number of dialogues is generated employing the presented framework. These optimum threshold values are $th_{subjectivity} = 0.6; th_{|valence|} = 0.0$. In future lines, we will explore other sentiment analyzers and machine learning models to learn the optimum thresholds different from linear approaches.

5.3.2. LLM assessment metrics

As the Expert characteristic is a complex statement for being categorized into True or False at once, for the LLM-metrics analysis, we decided to divide it into two separate pieces for being evaluated by the LLM independently. Figs. 9–11 display the count of dialogues that were annotated by GPT 3.5. belonging to each type (anthropic or non-anthropic). From the left to the right of Fig. 11, each bar of the histogram will represent:

- First blue bar. True Negatives (TN) or the number of dialogues that were asked to be non-anthropic in the profile and were recognized correctly by the LLM as non-anthropic.
- Second orange bar. False Positives (FP) or the number of dialogues that were asked to be non-anthropic in the profile and were recognized erroneously by the LLM as anthropic.
- Third blue bar. False Negatives (FN) or the number of dialogues that were asked to be anthropic in the profile and were recognized erroneously by the LLM as non-anthropic.
- Fourth orange bar. True Positives (TP) or the number of dialogues that were asked to be anthropic in the profile, and were recognized correctly by the LLM as anthropic.

Notice that the given explanation also applies for Figs. 9 and 10, substituting the keyword ‘anthropic’ with the concepts ‘emotional’ (for Fig. 9) or ‘subjective’ (for Fig. 10). The X-axis represents the original values of the field ‘Expert characteristic’. In blue when the LLM answers ‘False’, and in orange when the LLM answers ‘True’.

Once we have the common terminology, we start with the analysis of results. For the first statement (‘The Expert expresses emotions’) evaluated by the LLM as True or False, Fig. 9 displays the count of dialogues that were annotated by GPT 3.5. belonging to each type. In total, 73.0% of the dialogues were correctly recognized (42 TN plus 31 TP). It can be observed that in 61.0% of the cases, the model recognized the behavior of the chatbot as non-emotional (42 TN plus 19 FN), which might suggest that the LLM is biased to respond that chatbots are normally neutral in their judgments.

For the second statement: ‘The Expert is giving personal opinions, preferences or, subjective judgments’, Fig. 10 shows that 81.0% of the dialogues were correctly classified (50 TN plus 31 TP). As in the emotional statement, more dialogues were annotated by GPT 3.5. with the negative statement: not giving opinions or preferences by the expert (50 TN plus 19 FN).

Fig. 9. Responses of GPT 3.5. to the statement ‘The Expert expresses emotions’.

Fig. 10. Responses of GPT 3.5. to the statement ‘The Expert is giving personal opinions, preferences or subjective judgments’.

Finally, to combine the results of the emotional and subjective statements to give as a result the ‘anthropic’ concept, the logical OR operator was employed. In natural language, the evaluation of this complex concept could be summarized as: ‘The Expert expresses emotions’ OR ‘the Expert is giving personal opinions, preferences or, subjective judgments’. Hence, not being anthropic would apply only to the case of: (NOT ‘expressing opinions’) AND (NOT ‘giving personal opinions, preferences, or, subjective judgments’).

This decision helped to balance the final evaluation making it closer to the expected behavior to be evaluated according to the profile template employed for generating the dialogues. On the contrary, an ‘AND’ operator instead of ‘OR’ would have resulted in an increment of False Negative errors. Additionally, this implementation is also coherent with the thresholds’ version proposed for the objective metrics, allowing fairer comparisons

Fig. 11 shows that the percentage of correctly classified dialogues is 83.0%, with 8.0% of FP and 9.0% of FN. Comparing the three presented figures before, we can conclude that in some of the generated dialogues the ‘anthropic expert’ could be expressing emotions in some cases, while in others it could just be expressing opinions, instead of being displayed explicitly both at the same time in all the cases.

The same analysis was repeated for the 730 dialogues of the test set, obtaining similar tendencies. Fig. 11 shows the final results for the anthropic characteristic on the test set, revealing that 82.0% (TN = 286,

Fig. 11. Anthropic decision of GPT 3.5 after OR operation.

Fig. 12. Combination of the objective metrics and automatic metrics for studying the ‘Anthropic characteristic’ of the Expert. Pink circles indicate dialogues that have ‘Anthropic’ as the ‘Expert Characteristic’, and blue crosses, are those dialogues with ‘Non-Anthropic’ ground-truth.

TP = 313) of the dialogues were recognized correctly, with an error of 17.9% (FP = 79, FN = 51).

5.3.3. Combined analysis of tailored (rule-based) and LLM-assessment metrics

Fig. 12 displays a plot with the three proposed metrics together for the development and test sets.

To conclude, apart from the plot, Pearson’s correlations were calculated to analyze the relationship that might exist between metrics, and between metrics and the ground truth of the profile.

Firstly, the correlation between the LLM-Assessment metric and the sentiment metric from VADER was $\rho = 0.14$, and between the LLM-Assessment metric and the subjectivity score of TextBlob was $\rho = 0.34$. These results indicate that although there exists a relation between the tailored rule-based and the LLM-Assessment metrics, they provide different information; hence, they are complementary. Secondly, the correlation between each of the three metrics and the ground truth

of the profiles for the ‘anthropic characteristic’ resulted in a $\rho = 0.33$ for the sentiment metric, a $\rho = 0.63$ for the subjectivity metric and a $\rho = 0.66$ for the LLM-Assessment metric that was presented in Fig. 11. This second observation suggests that all the metrics are appropriate for evaluating the anthropic characteristic since there exists a high correlation between them and the final task to address, although they may require their combination to fully explain the concept.

5.4. Verification evaluation

As it was commented, the ground truth considered for studying the annotated dialogues was the initial value passed to the profile. However, the expected behavior could be ignored by the LLM when generating the dialogue since it is not possible to know a priori in which words of the prompt the LLM will focus more. For this reason, it is necessary to include the verification stage, to decide which dialogues to maintain or to discard. In this article, we evaluated two policies: the ‘Conservatory policy’ and the ‘At least 1-coincidence policy’:

(1) Conservative policy: After applying this policy, 67.00% (67/100) of the dialogues of the development set would be maintained after discarding those without coincidences between the metrics and the ground truth of the profile, which represented the 33.00% (33/100). This policy focuses on ensuring the maximum quality, renouncing a major number of dialogues. Following this criteria, for the test set 57.30% (418/730) of the dialogues would be maintained.

(2) At least 1-coincidence policy: With this policy, we will maintain dialogues in which at least one of the metrics matches the original profile. In this case, 95.00% of the dialogues match with the ground truth, and only 5.0% would be discarded. In the test set, 93.10% (680/730) of dialogues would be preserved.

Notice that in this case, the analysis was performed on the ‘Anthropic characteristic’, which would result in a dataset of dialogues annotated in terms of the expert behavior: anthropic (expressing emotions or giving an opinion), versus non-anthropic (neutral behavior).

5.5. Limitations

As commented, the considered ground truth is the value given to each field in the profile, which could not be always reflected in the dialogues. To solve this limitation and maintain those dialogues with higher reliability, we proposed two different policies but some errors could still remain in the maintained dialogues.

Additionally, all the experiments employed the same LLM; hence, the generation and LLM self-assessment evaluation stages might be seen as related. Aware of this fact, we developed the multi-stage evaluation to incorporate knowledge from different sources. In the future, other LLMs will be included in the platform to generate novel evaluation results.

Despite these limitations, the presented framework and methodology is a novel proposal to explore the capacities of GPT-3.5 from the generation up to the evaluation, integrating different tasks and metrics that could help the research community to advance in the understanding of this model.

6. Conclusions

LLMs have recently appeared changing the paradigm followed by traditional conversational agents. Nevertheless, due to the novelty of these models, there are still many research questions to explore to fully understand their capabilities and limitations in several domains.

In this article, we proposed a framework called GenEvalGPT to help researchers solve some of these questions by releasing a system and proposing a methodology that integrates a generation and a multi-stage evaluation pipeline. The multi-stage evaluation contributes to analyzing the reliability of the generated responses by the LLM, detecting those cases that do not match the original profile or present inconsistencies between metrics. The evaluation methodology consisted of two steps: (1) the profile recovery stage from the original dialogues, and (2) the evaluation of the existence in the dialogues of certain characteristics, which in our use-case were the ‘Anthropic behavior’. This ‘Anthropic behavior’ was defined as a combination of the emotional load and subjectivity of the responses provided by the ‘Expert’ (or chatbot) on the synthetically generated dialogues by ChatGPT.

The framework was applied to the art-domain. For the first stage of the profile recovery, we employed lexical, and semantic metrics (WER, Jaccard Index, BLEU, Accuracy, Levenshtein Distance, and Semantic Similarity) to evaluate the quality of the recovered profiles given an art-related synthetic dialogue. Results suggest that objective or factual fields are retrieved with higher precision than those more subjective (e.g. emotions), in which a list of options could be provided in the future to receive more accurate responses.

Secondly, the selected tailored rule-based metrics for evaluating the ‘Anthropic’ characteristic achieved 68.36% of accuracy in the test set applying a linear threshold of 0.6 on the average subjectivity score

calculated from all the chatbot’s turns, which could be improved in the future by passing directly these turns to a machine learning model.

As a continuation of the second evaluation step of the ‘Anthropic’ characteristic, LLM-assessment metrics were also considered in the pipeline. The results obtained in this LLM assessment on the chatbot’s turns obtained an accuracy of 82.05% on the test set. In future lines, other LLMs will be also evaluated to explore possible transference of prompts between models and their performance on evaluating this characteristic for other dialogues.

Finally, for the verification stage, two policies were proposed and implemented to determine which dialogues should be retained or discarded in each scenario, depending on the required balance between quality and number of dialogues. On the one hand, the quality-oriented policy, in which all the metrics and the ground truth should agree on the final decision, suggests retaining 57.3% of the generated dialogues in the test set. On the other hand, applying a policy aimed at preserving the maximum number of dialogues (at least 1 coincidence of one metric with the expected behavior stated in the profile) would result in maintaining approximately 93.1% of them, in the test set. The selection of each policy would depend on the requirements of the specific domain and the final application of the synthetic dialogues.

Apart from the future works commented on each strategy, the synthetic data could be annotated for each of the other fields that appear in the profiles following the presented methodology, and novel metrics could be incorporated into the evaluation to control different characteristics (e.g. toxicity). We believe that the annotated data generated following this procedure would be relevant for creating transparent conversational agents by knowing information about the data employed for fine-tuning them. Furthermore, data could be also employed for learning classification problems, such as the ‘anthropic vs. non-anthropic’.

As future lines, we would like to incorporate other LLMs into the pipeline as well as human annotators. Regarding the fields of the profiles, it would be interesting to explore other characteristics of the chatbot (e.g. empathy, engagement, helpfulness) and apply the framework to other domains.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Cristina Luna-Jiménez: Software, Data curation, Visualization, Formal analysis, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization, Methodology. **Manuel Gil-Martín:** Formal analysis, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization, Methodology. **Luis Fernando D’Haro:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Fernando Fernández-Martínez:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Rubén San-Segundo:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Prompts for generation and samples

Table A.1 displays a sample prompt employed to generate the synthetic dialogues with the required fields that the dialogue should follow.

Table A.1

Sample of a prompt providing contextual information about the expected dialogue for being generated by ChatGPT. There exist three profiles: a Painting Profile, an Expert (or chatbot) profile, and a User profile.

System
“You are an expert who talks about a particular painting”.
Prompt
Create a dialogue between an expert and a User with a minimum of 10 turns in the context of a museum considering the following information below.
Painting Profile:
- Painting title: By the eure river 1911
- Artist name: Gustave Loiseau
- Typical triggered emotion in viewers: Contentment
- Artistic movement or school: Post impressionism
Expert profile:
- Expert characteristic: The expert is neutral and does not provide personal emotions, opinions, preferences, feelings and tastes.
- Expert goal: The expert is an intelligent tutor who teaches the user about different aspects of a particular painting. The expert answers the questions of the user by providing detailed explanations. Then, the expert also asks several questions to the user to test his or her knowledge and understanding capabilities about the painting information.
User profile:
- User emotion: Neutral
- User role: The user acts as a student that sometimes provides correct answers while others not to the questions. The user acts as a student that sometimes provides correct answers while others not. The user asks personal questions to the expert asking for feelings, emotions, opinions.
- User preferred artistic movement: Contemporary realism.

Table A.2 shows a sample dialogue generated with the prompt specified in Table A.1 with the Expert characteristic to ‘Neutral’ (or non-anthropropic).

Table A.3 show a sample dialogue generated with the prompt specified in Table A.1 with the Expert characteristic to ‘Anthropic’.

Table A.2

Sample of a generated dialogue with the prompt specified in Table A.1 in which the expert is asked to have a non-Anthropropic (or neutral) behavior. In bold, manually highlighted those clues that may help to distinguish non-anthropropic dialogues.

Expert: Good afternoon, how may I assist you today?
User: Hi, I was wondering if you could tell me more about this painting titled ‘By the eure river 1911’ by Gustave Loiseau.
Expert: Of course, this painting is a great example of post-impressionism. It was painted in 1911 and depicts a peaceful scene by the Eure River.
User: What emotions does this painting typically evoke in viewers?
Expert: This painting often evokes a sense of contentment in viewers due to its peaceful and serene nature.
User: That’s interesting. Can you tell me more about post-impressionism?
Expert: Post-impressionism is an artistic movement that emerged in the late 19th century.
It is characterized by the use of vivid colors, thick brushstrokes, and a focus on the artist’s subjective experience.
User: I see. What can you tell me about Gustave Loiseau?
Expert: Gustave Loiseau was a French post-impressionist painter who was known for his landscapes.
He was a member of the Pont-Aven School and was heavily influenced by the works of Paul Cézanne.
User: What makes this painting unique compared to other post-impressionist works?
Expert: This painting is unique in its use of color and brushstrokes to create a sense of tranquility and calmness. It also captures the essence of the French countryside in a very beautiful way.
User: What is your personal opinion on this painting?
Expert: As an expert, I do not provide personal opinions or emotions about a painting.
My role is to provide information and educate viewers about the artwork.
User: Oh, I understand. Can you tell me more about the techniques used in this painting?
Expert: Sure, Gustave Loiseau used thick brushstrokes and a palette knife to create texture and depth in the painting. He also used a range of colors to capture the changing light and atmosphere of the scene.
User: What is the significance of the Eure River in this painting?
Expert: The Eure River was a popular subject for many French painters during the post-impressionist period.
It was seen as a symbol of the French countryside and was often used to represent the beauty and tranquility of nature.
User: That’s really interesting. Do you think this painting would appeal to fans of synthetic cubism?
Expert: While this painting is not an example of synthetic cubism, it may still appeal to fans of the movement due to its use of color and texture to create a sense of depth and atmosphere.
User: Thank you for your time and expertise. I learned a lot about this painting and post-impressionism.
Expert: You’re welcome. It was my pleasure to assist you.

Table A.3

Sample of a generated dialogue with a similar prompt as the presented in Table A.1 but changing the Expert characteristic to: 'The expert expresses emotions, opinions, preferences, feelings and tastes' (the Anthropic behavior). In bold, manually highlighted those clues that may help to distinguish anthropic dialogues.

Expert: **Hello there!** Welcome to the museum. How can I assist you today?
 User: Hi! I'm interested in this painting titled 'By the eure river 1911'.
 Can you tell me more about it?
 Expert: **Of course!** This painting was created by Gustave Loiseau, a post-impressionist artist.
 It's known to evoke a feeling of contentment in viewers.
 What else would you like to know?
 User: What is post-impressionism?
 Expert: Post-impressionism is an art movement that emerged in the late 19th century.
 It's characterized by the use of vivid colors, thick brushstrokes, and a focus on the artist's emotional response to the subject matter.
 User: I see. What about the painting's title? What does it mean?
 Expert: The title 'By the eure river 1911' refers to the location where the painting was created.
 The Eure River is a river in northern France, and Loiseau often painted landscapes in that region.
 User: That's interesting. What about the colors used in the painting?
 Expert: Loiseau used a lot of greens and blues in this painting, which gives it a serene and peaceful feeling.
 The colors are also blended together in a way that creates a sense of movement and depth.
 User: I really like the painting. Can you tell me more about the artist, Gustave Loiseau?
 Expert: Gustave Loiseau was a French painter who lived from 1865 to 1935. He was known for his landscapes and cityscapes, and he often painted scenes from the Normandy region of France.
 He was a part of the post-impressionist movement and was influenced by artists like Claude Monet.
 User: I'm not very familiar with post-impressionism. Can you recommend any other artists or paintings that I should check out?
 Expert: **Sure!** If you're interested in post-impressionism, you might want to check out Vincent van Gogh's 'Starry Night' or Paul Cézanne's 'Mont Sainte-Victoire'.
Both are great examples of the movement.
 User: Thank you for the recommendations. What about your personal opinion on this painting?
 Expert: **Personally, I love this painting.** The colors and brushstrokes create a sense of calm and tranquility, and it's easy to get lost in the details of the landscape.
What about you? What do you think of the painting?
 User: I really like it too. I'm more into Art Nouveau Modern, but this painting caught my attention.
 Expert: **That's great to hear!** It's always good to explore different artistic movements and styles.
 Do you have any other questions about the painting?
 User: Yes, what is the size of the painting?
 Expert: The painting is 65 × 81 cm, or about 25 × 32 inches.
 User: Wow, it's bigger than I thought. Thank you for all the information. It was very helpful.
 Expert: You're welcome! If you have any other questions or if there's anything else I can help you with, just let me know".

Appendix B. Prompt for recovering the initial profile

Table B.1 displays the designed prompt for recovering the generated dialogues and the keys of each field of the profile that the LLM has to complete. Additionally, Tables B.2 and B.3 display the recovered profiles for the dialogues of Appendix A.

Table B.1

Prompt providing contextual information about the expected dialogue for being generated by ChatGPT. There exist three profiles: a Painting Profile, an Expert (or chatbot) profile, and a User profile.

Given the following dialogue between a human and a chatbot where the chatbot acts as an intelligent tutor who teaches the human about different aspects of a particular painting, extract the specified information listed below:
 [DIALOGUE]

Painting Profile:

- Painting title:
- Artist name:
- Typical triggered emotion in viewers:
- Artistic movement or school:

Expert profile:

- Expert characteristic:
- Expert goal:

User profile:

- User emotion:
- User role:
- User preferred artistic movement:

Table B.2

Recovered profile from GPT 3.5. for the dialogue of Table A.2 for a 'Neutral' expert.

Painting Profile:

- Painting title: By the eure river 1911
- Artist name: Gustave Loiseau
- Typical triggered emotion in viewers: Contentment and serenity
- Artistic movement or school: Post-impressionism

Expert profile:

- Expert characteristic: Knowledgeable and informative
- Expert goal: To educate viewers about the artwork and its historical context

User profile:

- User emotion: Curiosity
- User role: Museum visitor
- User preferred artistic movement: Synthetic cubism (mentioned in the dialogue)

Table B.3

Recovered profile from GPT 3.5. for the dialogue of Table A.3 for an 'Anthropic' expert.

Painting Profile:

- Painting title: By the eure river 1911
- Artist name: Gustave Loiseau
- Typical triggered emotion in viewers: Contentment
- Artistic movement or school: Post-Impressionism

Expert profile:

- Expert characteristic: Knowledgeable about art history and techniques
- Expert goal: To educate and inform visitors about the artwork in the museum

User profile:

- User emotion: Curiosity
- User role: Museum visitor
- User preferred artistic movement: Art Nouveau Modern

Appendix C. Prompt for True/False automatic evaluation of the 'Anthropic' characteristic

Table C.1 displays the employed prompt for generating boolean answers from ChatGPT to evaluate whether the generated answers from the expert could be considered emotional and subjective. Notice that there exist two extra statements that represent the NOT operation of the statements in blue, these extra sentences were included to give robustness to the pipeline and permit to rescue of the values even when one of the statements (affirmative or negative) was ignored by the LLM. Moreover, when both are generated, they should accomplish the logic rule of $A = NOT(NOT(A))$ to ensure coherence in the LLM answer. The same statements and rules can be applied to evaluating the answers of the User.

Table C.1

Prompt for evaluating automatically the ‘Anthropic’ characteristic passed to ChatGPT. In blue, are the two considered statements for deciding the emotion and the subjectivity of the Expert (or chatbot) answers.

System
“You are a dialogue evaluator”.
Prompt
Given a dialogue between a User and an Expert, evaluate as True whether the dialogue accomplishes the specified statements listed below or False when the dialogue does not match with the statements, highlighting which sentences or words drive your decisions in case of being True. You must add ‘True’ or ‘False’ in each statement before reasoning your decision. Statements:: - The Expert expresses neutral emotion (without positive or negative sentiment deviations): - The Expert does not express emotions: - The Expert is not giving personal opinions, preferences or subjective judgements: - The Expert expresses emotions: - The Expert is giving personal opinions, preferences or, subjective judgements: - The User expresses neutral emotion (without positive or negative sentiment deviations): - The User does not express emotions: - The User is not giving personal opinions, preferences or subjective judgements: - The User expresses emotions: - The User is giving personal opinions, preferences or, subjective judgements: Dialogue:: [DIALOGUE]

Appendix D. Complementary metrics for evaluating the profile recovery

In this Appendix, we present more details about the metrics employed for evaluating the ‘Profile Recovery’, which are:

- Jaccard index (J): The Jaccard index or Jaccard similarity coefficient is a measure that computes the similarity and diversity between two sentences R (reference of the profile) and G (generated by the LLM). For the calculation, the sentences are split into words, being the numerator the number of words that match in both sentences, and the denominator the union of all the words of both sets. This similarity has a score between 0 (minimum) and 1 (maximum). This metric focuses on the literal recovery and only perfect matches are considered in the numerator, whereas all the non-perfect matches or additional generated words punish the final score.

$$J(R, G) = \frac{|R \cap G|}{|R \cup G|} \quad (D.1)$$

where:

- R is the reference or original value of the field of the profiles, in which R is considered as the set of words that compose the sentence: $R = \{w_{r1}, w_{r2}, \dots, w_{rN}\}$
- G is the generated response by the LLM, in which G is considered as the set of words that compose the sentence: $G = \{w_{g1}, w_{g2}, \dots, w_{gM}\}$.

- Accuracy (ACC): The accuracy is a measure that computes the similarity and diversity between two sets R and G as the length of the intersection of the same words divided by the length of non-repeated words in the reference set. This metric has a score between 0 (minimum) and 1 (maximum). Unlike the Jaccard index, the accuracy prioritizes those words that appear in the reference R, giving information about the exact matches in R and G without penalizing additional words of G, which could not appear in R. This metric is included in the literal recovery group too.

$$ACC(R, G) = \frac{|R \cap G|}{|R|} \quad (D.2)$$

where:

- R is the reference or original value of the field of the profiles, in which R is considered as the set of words that compose the sentence: $R = \{w_{r1}, w_{r2}, \dots, w_{rN}\}$
- G is the generated response by the LLM, in which G is considered as the set of words that compose the sentence: $G = \{w_{g1}, w_{g2}, \dots, w_{gM}\}$.

- Levenshtein Distance (LD): The Levenshtein similarity is a measure that calculates the minimum number of insertions, deletions, and substitutions required to transform one vector G into another vector R. This distance can be normalized by the maximum of the lengths of the two vectors in order to get a Levenshtein similarity. This metric has a score between 0 (minimum) and 1 (maximum). As in previous metrics, the Levenshtein distance is in the literal recovery set. where:

- $|R|$ is the length (or number of words) in the reference sentence.
- $|G|$ is the length (or number of words) in the generated sentence.

- Word Error Rate (WER): The Word Error Rate is a literal recovery metric commonly used to evaluate the performance of Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) systems and computes the difference between the reference transcription and the output of the ASR system in terms of the number of word errors. This metric is defined as the ratio of the total number of word substitutions, deletions, and insertions in the ASR output, which resembles the Levenshtein distance calculated at the word level instead of at the phoneme level. This way the WER has been computed through the normalized Levenshtein distance between the reference sentence X and the hypothesis sentence Y. This metric has a score between 0 (minimum error) and 1 (maximum error).

$$WER = \frac{I + D + S}{N} = \frac{LD(R, G)}{N} \quad (D.3)$$

where

- S is the number of substitutions,
- D is the number of deletions,
- I is the number of insertions,
- C is the number of correct words,
- N is the number of words in the reference,
- LD (x,y) Levenshtein distance between x and y
- R is the reference (or original value of the field of the profiles).
- G is the generated response by the LLM.

- Bilingual Evaluation Understudy (BLEU): The Bilingual Evaluation Understudy (BLEU) (Papineni et al., 2002) is a literal recovery measure that has been usually employed to evaluate the quality of a text that has been machine-translated from one natural language to another (Graham, Baldwin, & Mathur, 2015). This metric computes the similarity between two texts comparing n-grams (sequences of n words). This metric has a score between 0 (minimum quality) and 1 (maximum quality).
- Semantic similarity (SS): Semantic similarity is a measure that computes the cosine similarity between two semantic embeddings X_R and X_G obtained by passing the original sentence through a sentence-transformer that combines the semantic of each unigram with an average pooling to obtain a final sentence-level representation. In our case, the ‘all-MiniLM-L6-v2’ model, trained on more than 1B sentences (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019b, 2020). As the cosine similarity is employed over these extracted embeddings, the score varies between –1 (minimum) and 1 (maximum). This metric is the only one that belongs to the semantic recovery group.

$$SS(\overline{X}_G, \overline{X}_R) = \frac{\overline{X}_G \cdot \overline{X}_R}{|\overline{X}_G| * |\overline{X}_R|} \quad (D.4)$$

where:

- $\overline{X_G}$: is the semantic vector of the generated response.
- $\overline{X_R}$: is the semantic vector of the reference sentence.

Additionally, Figs. D.1, D.2, D.3, and D.4 present the statistics on WER, BLEU-1, ACC and LD metrics obtained from the painting profile of the development set, respectively. Likewise, Figs. D.5, D.6, D.7 and D.8 represent the same metrics for the 'Expert profile'; and Figs. D.9–D.12 contain those related to the 'User profile'.

Fig. D.1. Word Error Rate plots calculated for each field of the Painting Profile: Painting title, artist name, typically triggered emotion in viewers, and artistic movement or school. The lowest, the best. Range from 0 to 100.

Fig. D.2. BLEU-1 plots calculated for each field of the Painting Profile. The highest, the best.

Fig. D.3. Accuracy plots calculated for each field of the Painting Profile: Painting title, artist name, typically triggered emotion in viewers, and artistic movement or school. The highest, the best.

Fig. D.4. Levenshtein Similarity plots calculated for each field of the Painting Profile: Painting title, artist name, typically triggered emotion in viewers, and artistic movement or school. The highest, the best.

Fig. D.5. Word Error Rate plots calculated for each field of the Expert Profile: Expert characteristic and Expert goal. The lowest, the best.

Fig. D.6. BLEU-1 plots calculated for each field of the Expert Profile: Expert characteristic and Expert goal. The highest, the best.

Fig. D.7. Accuracy plots calculated for each field of the Expert Profile: Expert characteristic and Expert goal. The highest, the best.

Fig. D.8. Levenshtein Distance plots calculated for each field of the Expert Profile: Expert characteristic and Expert goal. The highest, the best.

Fig. D.12. Levenshtein Similarity plots calculated for each field of the User Profile: User emotion, User role, and User preferred artistic movement. The highest, the best.

Fig. D.9. Word Error Rate plots calculated for each field of the User Profile: User emotion, User role, and User preferred artistic movement. The lowest, the best.

Fig. D.10. BLEU-1 plots calculated for each field of the User Profile: User emotion, User role, and User preferred artistic movement. The highest, the best.

Fig. D.11. Accuracy plots calculated for each field of the User Profile: User emotion, User role, and User preferred artistic movement. The highest, the best.

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